

Popular Article

Monkeypox Virus Infection: A Re-emerging and neglected zoonoses

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Introduction

The world community has not entirely recovered from the troubles caused by the novel COVID-19 pandemic, the emergence of a disease in several countries has started to concern the globe again. The disease is Monkeypox (MP), caused by a zoonotic orthopox DNA virus, which is related to virus that causes smallpox. The name Monkeypox was given as the virus was first detected in the year 1958 in monkeys kept for scientific research. In humans, MP infection was first described in the year 1970 in Democratic Republic of Congo. Since then, several sporadic outbreaks of MP infection have been reported in Africa because of contact with a wild reservoir of infection, mainly rodents. The MP virus has been circulating for decades in endemic regions of Africa, but scientific knowledge in this field is still lacking. In Africa, the MP outbreaks have been reported to occur for years but the disease was neglected and no combat measures were put into place. In recent times, the diversion of the diagnostic facilities, treatment protocols and public health surveillance towards COVID-19 might have paved a way for the MP infection to enter in human settings profoundly. The scientific fraternity still does not know precisely about the animals harboring MP virus in natural settings; however, the virus does circulate among rodents and is zoonotic in nature.

Current scenario:

Until April 2022, the MP infection cases were rarely reported from any other continents other than African regions. However, the number of cases has shown a rise from May 2022, wherein more than 3000 MP virus cases have been reported in more than 50 countries. Sensing an emergency, on June 23, 2022, the World Health Organization (WHO) declared MP as an “evolving threat of moderate public health concern”. Additionally, the WHO has also declared MP a "public health emergency of international concern". According to the WHO and United Nations (U.N.) data, from late June 2022 to early July 2022, there has been a rise of 77% in MP infection cases. As of August 08, 2022, the number of MP confirmed cases in 88 countries is 30,189. Among these, 29,844 cases have occurred in countries that have not historically reported this disease, including India. In India, the first MP case was reported in Kerala on 14th July, affecting a 35-year-old person who returned from UAE. In India, until 8th August, 2022, six cases of MP infection have been confirmed.

Timeline of MP cases

SI. No.	Year	Countries affected	No of confirmed cases
1.	1970	DRC	n=1
		Sierra Leone	n=1
		Liberia	n=1
2.	1971	Nigeria	n=2
		Ivory coast	n=1
3.	1976	Cameroon	n=2
4.	1978	Nigeria	n=1
5.	1981	Ivory Coast	n=1
6.	1984	CAR	n=6
7.	1987	Gabon	n=3
8.	1990	Cameroon	n=4
9.	1991	Gabon	n=5
10.	2003	Republic of Congo	n=11
		USA	n=47
11.	2005	Sudan	n=19
12.	2010	CAR	n=2
13.	2014	Sierra Leone	n=1
14.	2015	CAR	n=13
15.	2016	CAR	n=27
16.	2017	Central African Republic	n=8
		Liberia	n=2
		Republic of Congo	n=88
		Sierra Leone	n=1
17.	2017- 2018	Nigeria	n=89
18.	2018- 2021	Israel	n=1
		United Kingdom	n= 7
		Singapore	n=1

**Number of cumulative confirmed MP cases and deaths reported to WHO, by WHO Region,
from 1 January 2022 to 7 August**

SI. No.	WHO Region	Confirmed cases	Deaths
1.	African Region	375	7
2.	Region of the Americas	10,815	1
3.	Eastern Mediterranean Region	31	0
4.	European Region	16,495	2
5.	South-East Asia Region	13	1
6.	Western Pacific Region	85	0
7.	Cumulative	27,814	11

Host Range

The natural reservoir of MP virus and its maintenance cycle in natural settings has not been completely known yet. The MP virus has been isolated from several wild animals like non-human primates (orangutans, chimpanzees, sooty mangabeys, cynomolgus monkeys) and rodents (mice, rabbits, squirrels, hamsters, groundhogs and porcupines). Moreover, the susceptibility to this virus has been seen in anteaters, black-tailed prairie dogs, southern opossums, short-tailed opossums, marmosets and African hedgehogs.

Transmission routes

The MP virus can be transmitted via two routes: animal-human transmission and human-human transmission. The MP infection can pass onto the human population if bitten by an MP virus-infected animal or in contact with its blood, body fluids, or fur. It has also been speculated that the consumption of infected animals' meat without proper cooking can spread the infection. The human-to-human transmission can occur because of contact with an infected person's clothing materials, bedding or towels, used by the infected person with skin rashes, blisters or scabs. The air-borne transmission from infected to healthy person via cough or sneezing can also spread the infection. As per some experts, it is also suspected that the virus can be transmitted sexually. Moreover, vertical transmission and fetal deaths have also been described according to some reports. To date, the current spread of MP infection has

disproportionately affected men who are gay or bisexual, suggesting amplification of transmission via sexual networks.

MP virus variants

There are two variants of MP virus, viz., the Congo strain and the West African strain. The mortality rate in the Congo strain is more (10%), than the West African strain (1%). Moreover, the case fatality is more of Congo strain as compared to West African strain. Moreover, the Congo strain has more chances of human-to-human transmission than West African strain.

Risk group and risk factors

The young children and immunocompromised people, including persons having human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) infection, have been reported to be at higher risk for this infection. The symptoms of MP virus in immunocompetent individuals are mild, however, in immunocompromised individuals, children, elders, pregnant women and individuals with HIV and diabetes, the symptoms are severe. The risk factors for the current worldwide outbreak of MP infection in the human population may be due to changes in biological aspects of the virus, human behavioral changes, or both. These changes might be driven because of decreasing smallpox immunity, relaxation in COVID-19 preventive measures, resumption of international travel, and sexual interactions.

Drivers of re-emergence of MP infection

As the true cause for the re-emergence of the MP disease is still not known, but perhaps the most important driver for the worldwide resurgence of MP virus could be the cessation of smallpox vaccination since 1980, which has waned the immunity among the human population. Four decades after cessation of smallpox vaccination, the MP virus might have occupied the ecological and immunological niche that was once occupied by smallpox virus. Moreover, there is a demographic data that has revealed that the individuals who are affected with MP infection are aged 50 years or below. Other possible driver includes a sharp rise in MP affected cases in endemic areas, and thus there is a greater possibility of transmission of this virus to various other countries. The climate change could also be a driver for the re-emergence of MP, as historical data has suggested that MP outbreaks commonly occur during fall because of increased rainfall causing floods which drive animals to enter human settings. The lack or absence of active surveillance against MP infection could be another reason for the re-emergence of MP infection.

Symptoms of MP infection

The symptoms of MP infection start following an incubation period of 21 days. The symptoms are milder than smallpox infection and include fever, headache, myalgia or muscle pain, swollen lymph nodes, and exhaustion. The appearance of these symptoms is followed by the development of skin rashes, seen on the face usually and then spread to other body parts. The rashes form a scan and then shed off from body. The MP disease usually lasts for about 2-4 weeks. However, some complications like pneumonitis, encephalitis, keratitis, and secondary bacterial infections can also occur in MP infection.

Diagnosis of MP infection

The person showing MP symptoms should be tested for the confirmation of an MP virus infection. Laboratory diagnosis is based on nucleic acid amplification testing (NAAT), using real-time or conventional polymerase chain reaction (PCR) to detect viral DNA. The sample to be collected for MP confirmation is skin lesion material, swabs of lesion surface and/or the lesion exudates. In India, there are currently fifteen Virus research and diagnostic laboratories (VRDLs), which have been trained to perform diagnostic testing for MP virus infection along with ICMR-NIV Pune. Moreover, National Centre for Disease Control (NCDC) is also involved in testing of MP cases.

Treatment

Currently, any specific treatment is not available for curing MP infection. The infected person is medically advised to stay isolated so that there is no further transmission of the infection to others. Some clinical trials have shown that some antiviral drugs like tecovirimat, cidofovir, and brincidofovir are useful in treating MP cases. United States Food and Drug Administration (FDA) has given approval for using the antivirals-tecovirimat and cidofovir for the treatment of MP infection.

In terms of vaccines, there are some animal studies which have suggested that smallpox vaccination has shown effectiveness against MP infection. Moreover, the vaccination can also attenuate the MP disease outcome. The smallpox vaccines are being used in the United States for MP affected patients and are 85% effective. However, there are some documented adverse effects of smallpox vaccination mainly in immunocompromised individuals, and the vaccination can also elevate the recombination risk of MP virus and smallpox vaccine strain in coinfecting/superinfected patients. As these viruses are Orth poxviruses, their recombination is a major driver of evolution. Thus, there may be a risk of using smallpox vaccination in MP virus infection cases. The Vaccinia immune globulins are also an option for the treatment of

MP infection. These are antibodies obtained from pooled human plasma immunized with the smallpox vaccine and reserved for severely ill patients.

Myths and their explanations

In order to safeguard the human community against this dreadful disease, people should be well aware of the symptoms of MP infection as this infection show similarity with smallpox symptoms and thus can cause confusion among people. There are some false factual statements being continuously reported via social media posts. One of the reports says that MPV infection is the side effect of COVID-19 vaccine. This has created concern among the general population that whether the chimpanzee adenovirus vector used in AstraZeneca's COVID-19 vaccine is causing the MP infection outbreak. These social media posts do not have any scientific explanation about the claim regarding the COVID-19 vaccine's role in spreading MP virus infection. The vectors which are being used in COVID-19 vaccines have the role of acting as a carrier of vaccine components into the human cells, and do not contribute to developing any infection itself.

Vaccines being used to treat MP infection

The CDC has recommended vaccination for susceptible individuals and people exposed to the MP virus. The vaccination against smallpox has demonstrated 85% effectiveness in preventing MP infection due to cross-protection as well as causing milder illness. Previously, ACAM2000, an FDA-licensed live replicating vaccine was being used as a single dose vaccine for the prevention of smallpox. However, shedding of live viruses from the vaccination site can infect immunocompromised individuals who come into direct contact with a vaccinated individual leading to serious complications. In addition, myocarditis, pericarditis, brain or spinal cord involvement, vaccination site infection and/or eye infection have been reported following administration of ACAM2000.

At present, as original smallpox vaccines are no longer available to the general public, JYNNEOS, an FDA-approved and licensed live non-replicating virus vaccine is recommended for use in individuals above 18 years of age in the United States for the prevention of the MP and smallpox disease. JYNNEOS is a two-dose (0.5mL each) vaccine administered by the subcutaneous route, which is safe for use even in immunocompromised individuals. The second dose of JYNNEOS is given 4 weeks following first dose and it takes about 14 days after receiving the second dose for the immunity to reach its peak level. Recently, the U.S. FDA has granted authorization for emergency use of JYNNEOS via intradermal administration, allowing five doses to be delivered from a standard single-dose vial.

Actions to be taken to curb the spread of the MP virus

1. Presently, in non-endemic regions swift actions need to be opted to prevent the establishment of the MP virus in domestic as well as wildlife animals, mainly rodents.
2. In order to curtail the MP virus, spread in high-risk groups, there is a need to administer smallpox vaccination to provide cross-protection against MP.
3. Active MP surveillance in human populations, particularly in endemic regions, is needed.
4. Moreover, there is a need for periodic epidemiological surveillance of MP in rodents and small mammals.
5. There should be a public health regulation on trade, pet rodent's ownership, small mammals, and other wildlife animals.
6. There is a need to identify the specific MP virus reservoir which will fill knowledge gaps related to virus ecology, evolution and transmission dynamics.
7. As a preventive measure, the Center for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) has advised people to stay away from areas inhabited by the MP infected animals.
8. The infected persons should be put into isolation.
9. If a person has come in contact with the infected patient or animal, then immediately he or she should wash their hands properly with soap and water or use an effective alcohol-based sanitizer.
10. In healthcare settings, Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) kits are mandatory to wear while treating patients.

One Health Approach to curb the MP infection

In recent times, the novel zoonotic pathogens having epidemic potential are on rise. The continuous outbreaks caused by zoonotic pathogens like Ebola virus, Middle East Respiratory Syndrome, Coronavirus and now Monkeypox virus have highlighted the interconnectedness of humans, animals and environment. Thus, the One Health approach is needed to be deployed to effectively curb the emerging or re-emerging zoonotic outbreaks.

Conclusion

The current MP outbreak in >50 countries, including endemic and non-endemic regions, is a wake-up call for everyone. The outbreak has highlighted how little-to-no attention has been given to this virus spread within endemic areas. It is a reminder for everyone that in an inter-connected and globalized world, no region or country is safe from zoonotic pathogens unless they are efficiently contained. These faceless viruses do not know about borders. Thus,

the world has to move together in cohesion to fulfill knowledge gaps and contain various dreadful outbreaks.

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